

Editorial

Mind Body & Soul Harmony

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Psychophysiological science consider foundations of the mind is exemplified as Mental processes influence the physiological state of the body and changes in the body's physiology influence thoughts, feelings and motivational behavior. However, Harmony is a ubiquitous principle based on Motivations arise from physiological need to preserve the integrity of the organism, via processes and the ways we process or react to our environment depends on our internal bodily state. For example, if we are thirsty or hungry, the manner in which we behave toward food stimuli differs and biases perceptions, hedonics, cognitions and memory. Motivations drive behavior, while changes in the internal state of the body anticipate, facilitate or accommodate the consequences of motoric action. The result is an individual system in a state of vibrant instability internally that contributed to physical and social interaction with the external environment (Jonah L., 2009). The individual make-ups of character and behaviors has emerged out of such patterns of chemical release. The mind is supposed to be a virtual entity, one that reflects the workings of the neural networks, chemical and hormonal systems in our brain (Bennett, R. 2007 & Kaku, 2014). it cannot be localized to particular areas within the brain, though the entire cerebral cortex and deep grey matter form important components. Realization, sensitivity, conduct, intelligence, linguistic, impulse, energy, the urge to excel and intellect of the most complex kind are the product of the wide-ranging and multifaceted linkages between the different parts of the brain (Santoro, 2009). Likewise, anomalies attributed to the mind, such as the spectrum of illnesses dealt with by psychoanalysts are consequences of widespread aberrations, often in the chemical processes within different parts of the brain (Pinker S. 2003).

The Psychophysiological connections

Being content mean diverse things to different individuals as it can base on a moral extent like charity, kindness, responsiveness and values whereas others associate these with substantial wealth, decent professions and high principles of living. In any case the esoteric world it is recognized that to achieve a truly rewarding and fulfilling life one must gain balance between soul, mind and body. Congruence in the mind body and soul is the key to ultimate

wellness and contentment, and as such attaining this balance should be an important goal for every individual (O'Connor M., 2008 & Zeman A. 2007).

However, the understanding of physical and psychological existence of soul in connection with mind and body is still a rare thought. As most individuals rely on the phase and energy that is associated with the brain and body while totally ignoring the mind and soul (Jonah L.2009). We as humans are aware of highly-competitive culture with multi variant stress and burdens with fast paced life that lead to disproportion of mind, body and soul. With this happening the fulfillment and contentment reduces and sufferings emerges like stress, angst, unhappiness, fear, dullness, low self-assurance and hopelessness. As humans we need to trust the understanding of nature and its physical as well as psychological existence (Zeman A. 2007).

Let's take one at a time like the physical body; known to designed for basic communications related to essentials, aversions, sensual insights. The actions and reactions are focused via senses i.e. vision, odor, flavor, touch, and hearing. These are all mere reflections of inner being and give a clear indication of state mind, body and soul harmony. In Disordered mind, body and soul the out of alignment components lost the connections and the complex device of body become unserviceable (Pandya, S., 2011). Though the senses support the connection as with time they associate the way brain leads with adaptations in life choices and desires e.g. as brain get familiarize that it is in disharmony then the senses start mechanisms to satisfy an intellect of balance and harmony (Bennett, R. 2007).

the mind on the other hand can function at altered higher levels with the thought mechanism that energies our bodily experience (Kaku, 2014), it is

postulated that it works with the brain as it happens in new born with the intuition and desire of suckling depending on need while over time the mind loses this strong connection to intuition as stimuli in the milieu start to impact performance. The soul is the third important part and supposed as core of being (Santoro, 2009 & Jonah L.2009).

However, there are many cases reported when illness, mishaps or surgical procedures directly or indirectly resulted in altered behavior and personality with changes in memories, moods, and consciousness. A minor injury might even cause dramatic variations in personality. As brain is proven bench of self-awareness, intelligence, compassion, and ingenuity (O'Connor M., 2008). The neurotransmitters and psychopharmacological agents are also here to crush the idea of soul as these can do physiological alteration to bring an individual to good and peace. And neuroscience has strong evidence s that soul cannot overcome biology, that's why mental health can be lifted by the accurate medicine that shows the origin of moods as biological in nature ((Pandya, S., 2011). The frontal lobes that are the latest parts of our brains to develop from the gestation also proofs that small drip in blood sugar levels can hinder self-control as these lobes require lots of energy to operate normally. A lot of times behind crankiness, irritability and related negative emotions are due to low energy supply to prefrontal cortex (Santoro, 2009).

Cerebral good will, ease and lucidity

To bring upon the philosophical mind in early teens made individuals so deep-rooted in very young age and there are some good scientific views explaining this enrichment of thoughts that what world knows as 'strong soul'; science has always been the reason behind. Being a psychophysiolgist we are more influenced of the interpretations executed by brain as it received information via various spur and make us intellect well creature (Sadaf A. 2013a). These sets of information's are anthology from our right mind (Bennett, R. 2007), that percept an emotional upshot and feel connected with things, situations, people and places, but to put it in here the sway that make one's cognition and personality, so for the arriving information, the brain also have believed and past experience to be added in this fresh set of sensations. Behaviors are also the other side of the coin that represents not only the thoughts but the state of mental health and complexities in brain. While all these behavioral patterns may be altered and can be recognized as certain psychiatric illness both mild and severe-from weak and confused personality to

angry and hysteric personalities—these disturbances of brain functions affect feelings and thoughts. Getting stressed in life causes both positive and negative loops of our brain to stimulates, the positive one makes us more conscious, emotionally tough and to deem in ourselves, while negative one just grime minds with regrets, moan and undignified believes (Kaku, 2014). Now this is the reciprocated spot where psyche has its role to play and no soul is completed without this astonishing existence (Sadaf A. 2013 b). Researchers have revealed many previously unknown aspects of goodwill and concern that can convincingly enlighten pure side of soul. It does not only support the view of the emotions as rational, functional, and adaptive origins in Darwin's Expression of Emotion in Man and Animals but also support the view that empathy and kindness are essential features of human brain which have their role in evolved human nature, ingrained in brain and its physiology that can commence and nurture the spirit of goodness in human being. Our brains are all wired up to speak, to respond and to applaud and there are also recent evidences that realistically explain many worth experiencing human behaviors such as when a mother looks at her baby she experiences pure love compared to the sight of other children. It is also well demonstrated by distinctive bustle brain regions associated with the positive emotions, this could be related to other relations and associations as this wholesome impulse isn't restricted to parents' brains however it's an inborn human response entrenched into the wrinkled brain (Jonah L.2009 & Pandya, S., 2011). In other researches, the neuroscientists declared that serving relatives and others stimulate caudate nucleus and anterior cingulate i.e. the reward centers in brain which convey the feeling of bliss and satisfaction with our own will (Sadaf A. 2013 b). The brain seems wired up to respond to others' suffering without a doubt and it makes a mind feel good when one can ease misery of people around. There is also a slack involvement of Autonomic Nervous System (ANS) in adaptable blood flow and breathing patterns for different sort of events and related feelings. The ANS is responsible for various actual physiological alterations in heart rate that can be increased or slowed down. Oxytocin endorses attachment and dedications, as well as makes us the unique brand of nurturing deeds like concern, overpowering sentiment of affection and association we feel towards our dear ones. Indeed, breastfeeding and massages elevate oxytocin levels in the blood. An affectionate smile, a kind, responsive gesture and positive vibes can produce more oxytocin causing a

chemical reaction in the body that motivates us to be even more concerned (Sadaf A. 2013a). Expression of love, care, gratitude and pleasure through nonverbal signals also promote many adaptive functions to pacify people who are in pain or sorrow. It allows others to discover the goodness of souls of those with whom they feel connected and helps strengthen relationships. One of the most valuable nonverbal signals is touch, conveyed by human skin receptors that have the ability to convert pattern of tactile stimulation like a pat on the back or hug into deep-seated feelings. Many convincing and positive touches can elicit the release of oxytocin that adds up warmth and pleasure in such gestures (Sadaf A. 2013 b). Many researches also shed light on the collective functions of concern associated with the way people expect thankfulness and appreciation from loved ones that might rely on touch to soothe, reward, and bond in daily life that robustly points out human nature, a universal gift of communication and indulgence. Inspiring altruism is a precious feeling that reflects selfless behavior which not only fills up human capacity with moral opinions and social bonds but even allows us to be noble human beings and to act in a self-serving way, deeply rooted in human nature. It has natural roots from brain to body (Sadaf A. 2013a). Care and gratitude all the way through gestures and feel, and this exhibit of emotions, love and warmth can dish up collective life purposes that are full of essence and soul. On the other hand, evolution of human nature by experiences, selfish concerns and other mean motivations can lead to negative, down beat and egotistical apprehensions. Cultivation of this goodness, kindness, gratitude and thankfulness is a part of our heritable characteristics, recent studies in compassion also suggest that constructive emotions are less heritable and poorly determined by our DNA when compared with negative emotions and highly dependent on environmental input such as psycho-social impacts. Sometimes mind set up and decide to 'get honest mode' but these pleasures keep brain in denial of that honest voice within and the filthy voice with in

influence that I can't give up this pleasure!!! And individuals keep denying their thought processes (Pinker S. 2003). Mounting cerebral simplicity is an easier said than done task that can be an outcome of the mind's attitude reliant on inner instincts. The study of the brain, mind and soul has engaged some of the finest intelligences of pasts. It remains an ennobling and stirring quest, worthy of all those who are dedicated votaries of science.

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